

Defining the Team Principles

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

This exercise aims to **collectively discuss the principles of a collaboration**, such as meetings and meeting structure, communication styles and methods, roles and availability and process.

Benefits

This enhances understanding of diverse professional cultures and availabilities. It is ideal to do at the beginning of the consortium formation and include in any on-boarding activities with new partners as you have agreed principles of collaboration to refer to.

Practical recommendations

We suggest to run this exercise in one of the first meetings with the Multi-Actor project proposal group.

Introduction (10 min)

Introduce the activity as a way to talk about how you will work together on the development of the proposal. In this example, the exercise works with four areas: 1) Meetings structure and schedule, 2) Preferred method of communication, 3) Roles and availabilities and 4) Process. Put these four areas up on a (digital) whiteboard.

Round 1 – Gathering preferences from the group (10 min)

For each of the four areas, ask your participants to identify what their constraints (e.g., on a red sticky note) and recommendations (e.g., on a green sticky note) are. They are allowed to put down multiple sticky notes on each area. For example, if I am a farm advisor who is on the road part of the week, I would write on a red sticky note in the 'meetings area' that I cannot join meetings on these days.

Round 2 – Consolidating Team Principles (30 min)

Discuss within the group the different areas and sticky notes. On a different colour sticky note (e.g., blue), the facilitator can write down final decisions or action items the group agrees on.

This is a good way to gain a better understanding of the expectations and limitations of the different partners in your consortium.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

Defining the Team Principles by FunRetrospectives

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